

Advancing the Workforce That Supports Computationally and Data Intensive Research

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Research is increasingly dependent upon research computing and data (RCD) infrastructure, services, and most importantly, skilled professionals who can help facilitate researchers' use of technical resources. RCD professionals regularly co-learn research problems and co-create technical solutions alongside researchers, which is essential in domains new to compute/data-intensive methods. However, the roles of RCD professionals are poorly understood (e.g., relative to traditional/enterprise IT), and recruitment and retention of RCD professionals is challenging, in part due to a lack of clear career paths. Organizations such as the Campus Research Computing Consortium and Campus Champions (among others) have recognized these needs, and are creating products and services that are addressing these challenges. We describe the challenges, some of the progress made to date, and initiatives underway to support the development of a professional RCD workforce and to advance the state of RCD support.

Research is increasingly dependent upon cyber-infrastructure (CI) from instruments and sensors to high performance computing (HPC) and more. While HPC continues to be an important element, research computing and data (RCD) infrastructure and services have expanded well beyond HPC into secure enclaves for data compliance; big data management and analytics; artificial intelligence and machine learning (AI/ML); and more recently into heterogeneous compute models, edge computing, and cloud-based computing. The label "RCD" is inclusive of the broad range of infrastructure and services—and all the people—needed to support research, including computing,

storage, networking, virtualization, software, cybersecurity, etc. In a series of National Science Foundation (NSF)-funded Research Coordination Network (RCN) meetings in 2016–2017,² over 30 leaders in RCD met with organizational scientists who regularly study the progression from a community of practice to a profession, and deliberated the future course of the people supporting RCD. These meetings helped frame the importance of considering a future path of unique professionals that support scholarly discovery through the use of technology.

RCD was previously limited to physical sciences like chemistry and physics, but has expanded into all research domains as researchers move beyond the desktop and have greater RCD needs and requirements. Researchers are struggling to keep pace with the explosion of data and the rapid evolution of computing resources and often lack the skills to make full use of emerging tools and techniques. The challenges to researchers include the following:

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- › Constantly evolving computing and data tools, from HPC models to new modalities such as virtualization and cloud computing, and new hardware (e.g., FPGAs, quantum computing).
- › New instruments, sensor arrays, and analytic methods are producing vastly more data, which in turn require much more computation and new tools for data management, adding considerable complexity for researchers to manage.
- › In domains new to computationally and data-intensive methods, and for researchers adopting these techniques, they lack a tradition of use in their field, and often lack the needed skills to take advantage of emerging technologies and methodologies (e.g., graduate programs in domains new to computationally and data intensive research may not have included training in computational and data management methods).

The challenges of performance portability add an additional layer of complexity, requiring specific technical skills and experience that span traditional HPC architectures, as well as emerging accelerators, cloud computing, etc. Developing and maintaining this RCD expertise takes valuable time from research and is often beyond the capacity of researchers. As a result, researchers depend upon partners who combine technical expertise with an understanding of research workflows and researcher needs; these crucial roles constitute the emerging RCD profession. Although many of these roles are in academic research (e.g., universities and national labs), the work of RCD professionals is needed in other public sector organizations (e.g., NASA, Federal Reserve, NIST, NIH, and many other government laboratories and agencies) as well as in the private sector where research and development groups use computationally and data intensive methods.

In domains that have an established history of leveraging computing and data resources, researchers and students need help with evolving technology (e.g., new hardware and/or transitioning to cloud platforms), even as they build upon the training and practice they received during their education and previous experience. However, in domains that have more recently adopted computational and data intensive approaches, researchers often need a more fundamental form of support and introduction to computational and data management methods as well as to the evolving technology and services. A relatively modest amount of computation and data resources can make a major impact on research in these domains, and the balance of investment must be shifted from hardware to people in order to enable these researchers to take advantage of RCD resources. This need is rapidly growing: researchers in

the social sciences, for example, are using as much computing resources as physicists did ten years ago, and RCD programs are increasingly asked for resources in support of Digital Humanities applications.

NOT SURPRISINGLY, RCD PROFESSIONAL ROLES REQUIRE A DIFFERENT MINDSET, TRAINING, PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT, AND HUMAN RESOURCES (HR) SUPPORT AS COMPARED TO TRADITIONAL IT ROLES.

RCD is fundamentally different from traditional enterprise IT.³ The technologies (HPC systems, accelerators, etc.), goals, and requirements of researchers are all different, favoring highest performance, cutting-edge technology, open-source software, and the development of new algorithms over the stability, reliability, predictability, and standardization that is central to traditional enterprise IT services. In many cases, a research workflow is itself an experiment, and so emphasizes quick build cycles and a *fail fast* approach over careful needs analysis and service architecture considerations (i.e., once a workflow shows promise, and has wide appeal or application, a research architecture may be conducted, but this investment cannot be justified up front). Not surprisingly, RCD professional roles require a different mindset, training, professional development, and human resources (HR) support as compared to traditional IT roles. Lacking this support and because the roles are often poorly understood, institutions report considerable challenges recruiting and retaining RCD personnel.

Another important distinction is between RCD roles and researchers; although they often work closely together, RCD roles are *professional* and not primarily *academic* in nature. RCD professionals build deep expertise in the technology that supports research, whereas researchers primarily see technology as a means to discovery. RCD professional roles generally support many different domains (where researchers tend to focus deep in one), their work is primarily *service-oriented*, and unlike researchers, publishing and presenting is (at most) a secondary performance measure. Some RCD professionals have transitioned from an academic track, e.g., choosing not to pursue a faculty appointment but still wanting to stay engaged with research. Others were recruited from traditional IT environments and then trained in the technologies, approaches, and culture of the RCD domains. While researchers and RCD professionals share the need for a strong understanding of the

research process, the professional roles require a host of additional skills and disciplines that are specific and distinct from those of researchers.

CHARACTERIZING THE CHALLENGES

Almost as rapidly as technology is changing, the roles and responsibilities, formal positions, and possible career paths for RCD professionals are also evolving, posing serious challenges to providing effective research support services. The NSF-funded RCN meetings in 2016–2017 and the conclusions of the participants led to the formation of the Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC, carcc.org)—an organization of dedicated professionals developing, advocating for, and advancing campus RCD and associated professions. In an April 2017, CaRCC survey of RCD professionals at over 150 universities, colleges, and government labs, **professional development** was identified as the top priority. Soon thereafter the CaRCC RCD Professionalization Working Group was formed, and kicked-off with a two-day workshop in March 2018 that brought together 38 people from different backgrounds and institutions. Workshop participants identified several common themes that characterize RCD staff roles, in particular that **Career Paths are incomplete in most organizations, creating challenges for recruiting, developing, and retaining these professionals**. A tangible outcome of the March 2018 workshop was an initial draft of a *Research Computing and Data Professionals Job Elements and Career Guide*.⁷ As the draft guide was discussed and reviewed by the community, four key needs emerged:

- › RCD hiring managers reported **major challenges working with HR**, and the fact that existing job families for enterprise IT and research positions did not represent the breadth, diversity, and complexity of the RCD roles and responsibilities.
- › **RCD roles are evolving and changing at a rate that outpaces most university HR** reclassification processes.
- › **High-level individual contributor roles** equivalent to manager grades are needed so that technology leaders can emerge within the RCD domain, and not be forced to move elsewhere to advance their career.
- › Institutions face **challenges to evaluating positions for equity** when people are in positions that do not fully capture their job responsibilities.

In the Fall of 2020, an NSF-sponsored workshop *Building the Research Innovation Workforce* was held

“to identify new insights and directions to advance the research computing community.” The workshop gathered over 100 research computing leaders, practitioners, industry representatives, academic domain scientists, academic computing scientists, and attendees from federal agencies to explore key challenges and make recommendations to address these challenges.¹ The recurring themes echo those of the earlier workshops, but a number of new ones emerged as well:

- › The need for recognition and a clear definition of the different roles reflecting duties in the workforce.
- › The need for viable career paths with a reasonable level of funding and location stability, and the availability of training and education necessary for advancement and upskilling.
- › The need for a concerted effort to address diversity, equity, and inclusion as a systemic problem.
- › The need to formalize education and training to create a coherent body of transferable knowledge for the national community.
- › The creation of an “umbrella” organization spanning existing institutional, regional, and national organizations to advocate and coordinate actions and knowledge across the entire spectrum of roles, communities of practice, and institutions.
- › The need for an effective communication strategy to increase understanding, awareness, and acknowledgement of the essential role of cyberinfrastructure and research computing as a core element within the institutional research enterprise.

The issues described above are not limited to academia. As we engage in collaborations with industry and government entities and participate at local technology meet-ups, we encounter a similar pattern in which R&D groups operate akin to academic research labs, and have specialized technology support groups distinct from central/enterprise IT. This is especially true in the BioTech, Pharma, Life Science, and Engineering sectors, in which organizations leverage large amounts of analytics, modeling, and/or simulation. However, it extends into other sectors such as Finance where, for example, the Federal Reserve has a large HPC resource and investment banks and hedge funds deploy cutting-edge algorithms and computing environments for trading models, as well as in Law, where legal firms have compute and data intensive e-Discovery workflows. Representatives from these domains have started joining RCD professional communities like the Campus Champions and the CaRCC People Network and have

FIGURE 1. Research computing and data facings (roles).

expressed a strong desire to connect with their academic RCD peers who are facing similar challenges.

Although much of our work is focused in the U.S., these same challenges have been recognized internationally. The U.K.-based Society of Research Software Engineering (society-rse.org) describe a 2016 workshop that attracted participants from 14 different countries and “sparked the creation of related movements in countries around the world.” An EU Commission case study¹² noted the essential role of research software engineering, and found that “the skills needed to undertake this role and the career pathways in this field lack formality and do not receive the recognition they deserve.”

A SIMPLE TAXONOMY OF RCD PROFESSIONAL ROLES

Through the series of workshops mentioned above and in discussions within the community, a model for the range of RCD roles was developed with names that reflect who or what each role is *facing* (i.e., focused on). It is important to note that these are *roles* and not *individuals*, and many RCD professionals act in more than one of these roles. Originally described in a 2018 workshop report,³ the facings model has evolved to these five (presented previously at PEARC20¹⁰):

- 1) **Researcher Facing Roles.** These include RCD staffing, outreach, and advanced support, as well as support in the management of the research life-cycle. Example roles include: Research IT User Support, Research Facilitator, and CI Engineer (although at some institutions, this title may also be a Systems Facing role).
- 2) **Data Facing Roles.** These concern data creation; data discovery and collection; data analysis and visualization; research data curation, storage,

backup, preservation, and transfer; and research data policy compliance. Example roles include: Research Data Management Specialist, Data Librarian, and Data Scientist.

- 3) **Software Facing Roles.** These focus on software package management, research software development, research software optimization or troubleshooting, workflow engineering, containers and cloud computing, securing access to software, and software associated with physical specimens. Example roles include: Research Software Engineer and Research Computing Support.
- 4) **Systems Facing Roles.** These roles work with infrastructure systems, systems operations, and systems security and compliance. Example roles include: HPC Systems Engineer, Storage Engineer, and Network Specialist.
- 5) **Strategy and Policy Facing Roles.** These are responsible for institutional alignment, culture for research support, funding, and partnerships and engagement with external communities. Example roles include: Research IT leadership.

In a small RCD organization, one or two individuals may cover all of these different roles where a large center may have a team associated with each facing. While performance portability might be most associated with software-facing roles (and expertise), total performance considerations can span hardware, software, data movement/management, and the research goals, illustrating the range of skills that must come to bear to effectively support researchers.

CURRENT WORK TO ADDRESS THE CHALLENGES

A CaRCC working group on RCD Professionalization developed the **RCD Job Family Matrix and Guide**,⁷ the first national effort to provide a template that RCD Hiring Managers can use in discussion with their respective administrative and HR Leadership. This framework includes a job series for each of the facings, and is flexible enough to be used as a template by a range of institutions, whether large or small, public or private, degree granting, or purely research.

In addition, CaRCC is working to understand the state of RCD staffing across the country. Most institutions, especially with respect to HR organizations, are isolated from one another with regard to basic information on staffing size, position types, and pay grades. Many professional societies publish an annual salary survey (e.g., IEEE) as do some marketing firms (e.g.,

Dice), but none of these focus purely on academic institutions, and this makes it challenging for local HR to interpret and make use of them. The CaRCC RCD Professionalization working group launched a RCD Workforce Survey to inquire about staffing across the RCD facings, associated pay ranges, institutional demographics, job turnover, and position type (e.g., permanent versus term-based). The data gathered through this survey will be summarized and reported to the community.

While these are important steps forward, a number of challenges remain for recruitment and retention. RCD roles are not widely understood, and people considering these jobs have little idea why they might consider a career in RCD, how to prepare for these opportunities, and where they can lead. At the same time, hiring managers (and their HR representatives) do not know where to look for candidates that could be a good fit (i.e., how to find people who combine the necessary technical expertise with an understanding of research workflows). These are serious barriers to recruitment and to growing a “pipeline” into these roles.

FOR INDIVIDUAL STAFF CURRENTLY IN RCD ROLES, THERE IS A LACK OF RESOURCES TO HELP THEM GROW INTO NEW ROLES AND, MORE GENERALLY, TO CREATE A PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN.

For individual staff currently in RCD roles, there is a lack of resources to help them grow into new roles and, more generally, to create a professional development plan. The lack of a clear career path is frustrating, and it leads at least some of staff to pursue opportunities in other domains (often unrelated roles in the industry). Retention issues are especially acute for researcher-facing and data-facing roles. Recognizing this challenge, the CaRCC RCD Professionalization working group is currently gathering a set of example narratives and working toward a framework to describe RCD Career Arcs. These efforts recognize the range of educational and professional paths that can lead to RCD roles, and the various directions an individual can pursue to grow their career (e.g., deep technical expertise or domain knowledge, management, and leadership, and/or options outside of academia). In addition to providing a resource for professional development, this work may provide an analytic tool

to identify gaps and needs for missing training programs that will facilitate the transition from other positions into RCD roles, and, e.g., help develop existing RCD staff into RCD leadership roles.

Finally, RCD leadership roles face numerous organizational and cultural challenges. Many institutions—especially smaller and under-resourced institutions—are just coming to grips with RCD support needs, and need guidance to boot-strap, grow, and sustain their programs. In addition, campus leadership at many institutions lacks an appreciation of the increasing importance of RCD professional services to support campus researchers. Without robust support, faculty often build their own *ad hoc* resources (e.g., local clusters, *ad hoc* storage systems, etc.), and this creates many security and compliance issues, inefficiencies (e.g., underutilization compared to shared systems, poor data transfer performance, etc.), and major challenges for sustainability, not to mention all the time and energy devoted to infrastructure rather than research.

RCD professionals in strategy and policy-facing roles are seeking resources to more effectively communicate to campus leadership the distinction between RCD professionals and enterprise IT roles, and the value of investing in leading RCD practices. They are also asking for help with strategic planning and the development of sustainable models that can keep pace with the rapid growth in demand from researchers. Responding to this, Internet2, CaRCC, and EDUCAUSE collaborated with a diverse set of institutions to develop the RCD Capabilities Model (RCD CM).¹⁰ The model and an associated assessment tool allow institutions to assess their support for computationally and data intensive research, to identify potential areas for improvement, and to understand how the broader community views RCD support. The Model supports a range of stakeholders and provides structured input to guide strategic planning and enable benchmarking relative to peer institutions. In the first year after its release in early 2020, the assessment tool was downloaded by over 120 institutions representing 44 U.S. states and several Canadian provinces (including nearly half of all R1 and R2 research universities). Forty-one institutions completed assessments using the RCD CM and contributed these to a 2020 Community Dataset. Each contributing institution received an individualized benchmarking report, and all of them reported that they plan to use this report as input to strategic planning, with many also planning to use it to justify program funding and/or to support a grant proposal.¹¹

The community of RCD professionals is beginning to find a shared voice as they address these challenges. Several organizations have broad community participation: the CaRCC People Network (carcc.org/)

people-network/) has over 1000 members representing 236 universities (16 of them international), 26 not-for-profits, and 11 companies; and the Campus Champions (described below) has over 700 members at 300 + institutions, including many minority-serving colleges and universities. RCD Professionals in these and related organizations are calling for a more unified community of organizations to gather and support them, to promote understanding of the whole of the RCD profession, to clearly communicate challenges as well as opportunities, and to provide a shared voice advocating for the profession. Those in leadership roles (especially in emerging RCD programs) are calling for resources that will help them understand and implement leading practices for building and sustaining effective RCD programs and teams.

A new NSF-funded Cyberinfrastructure Centers of Excellence⁶ pilot will develop a Research Computing and Data Resource and Career Center that provides institutions and individuals with the products, tools, services, and community to build and sustain successful RCD operations. The grant will support the development of a more robust and sustainable implementation of the RCD Capabilities Model, resources for staff training and workforce development, including leading practices for recruitment, onboarding, advancing diversity, equity, and inclusion, and professional development, as well as proven models for student internship and training programs. Much of this will build upon work begun in CaRCC working groups, but the team plans to use the pilot phase to facilitate the creation of a coordinating organization that connects all the relevant communities that can benefit from RCD support and develop a shared voice for RCD professionals.

THE COMMUNITY OF ORGANIZATIONS SUPPORTING RCD PROFESSIONALS

One indicator of the growth and maturing of an RCD profession are many communities in the RCD ecosystem that recognize, support, and provide development opportunities for RCD professionals as distinct from enterprise information technologists. Although this list is by no means inclusive of the entire set of communities supporting and advocating for RCD professionals, these groups are among those active in this space:

- › The Campus Research Computing Consortium (CaRCC^a) is an organization of dedicated

professionals developing, advocating for, and advancing campus research computing and data and associated professions. CaRCC's community building efforts focus largely around the RCD professionals through the People Network, an ongoing virtual conference/community for campus professionals that connects the broader research computing and data ecosystem, addresses professionalization and workforce development, and defines stakeholders and shared value propositions for the community at a time of accelerating change.

- › Internet2^b is a not-for-profit membership organization that provides high speed networking, services tailored for research and education, and other research support. Internet2 leads efforts with the NSF to identify research workforce issues (among other RCD topics), and has developed strong partnerships with CaRCC and Campus Champions to regularly cosponsor projects and other efforts in support of RCD professionals.
- › EDUCAUSE^c is a nonprofit membership association of technology, academic, industry, and campus leaders advancing higher education through IT, sponsors the Research Computing and Data Community Group, and other activities addressing RCD support topics including white papers and community surveys and polls on topics that are driving research and research support.
- › The Coalition for Academic Scientific Computation (CASC)^d is an educational nonprofit membership organization dedicated to advocating for the use of the most advanced computing technology to accelerate scientific discovery. CASC supports economic and workforce development in high performance computing-related fields, collaborating with partners like the United Kingdom High Performance Computing Special Interest Group (HPC-SIG) and CaRCC.
- › The Campus Champions (CC^e)—originally the Extreme Science and Engineering Discovery Environment (XSEDE) CC—has matured into a large community of RCD professionals, mostly on campuses, with bimonthly virtual get-togethers and information sharing sessions and a vibrant email list answering questions about RCD topics across the facings.

^a <https://www.carcc.org>

^b <https://www.internet2.edu>

^c <https://www.educause.edu>

^d <https://casc.org>

^e <https://campuschampions.org>

- › The US Research Software Engineer Association (RSE^f) gathers professionals who identify with the software-facing roles (if not the title) of a Research Software Engineer. The group aims to provide the members of the community the ability to share knowledge, professional connections, and resources; to promote RSEs' impact on research; and to provide useful resources to multiple demographics.

Several initiatives are working to professionalize the cybersecurity aspects of RCD roles. This expertise has growing importance, for example, as health sciences research is increasingly data-driven and secure environments are a prerequisite for using shared computing and data systems (from HPC to cloud environments). The same is true about areas of social sciences research that involve sensitive populations, urban engineering research using utility-providers' data, and many others. The Cybersecurity Maturity Model Certification from the U.S. Department of Defence^g and President's Biden's Executive Order on Cybersecurity⁹ are examples of the growing regulatory and compliance requirements that researchers face (not to mention the sophisticated and persistent cybersecurity threats to research results and intellectual property). Initiatives supporting the intersection of RCD professionalization and cybersecurity include the NSF-sponsored Research Security Operations Center (ResearchSOC^h), which is introducing "research facilitation" principles to IT security professionals, and TrustedCI (TrustedCIⁱ), an NSF Cybersecurity Center of Excellence working to develop the workforce, knowledge, processes, and cyberinfrastructure that enables trustworthy science.

THE PROFESSIONALIZATION OF RCD ROLES TO ADVANCE WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT

Among the discussions across the community about how best to address challenges we face has been a call to more formally define an RCD profession. *Professionalization* is generally used to mean the process of building a legitimate, widely recognized profession out of a loose or emerging occupational category. The RCD community has explored aspects of professionalization and identified specific goals (and some non-goals) that will help address some of the challenges we face.

^f <https://us-rse.org>

^g <https://www.acq.osd.mil/cmmc>

^h researchsoc.iu.edu

ⁱ <https://www.trustedci.org/>

Law, accounting, and medicine are examples of well-established professions with educational standards, formal qualifications, and governing bodies. Such professions are communities of well-vetted, trusted specialists in their particular domains, and enjoy a level of legitimacy among key stakeholders, particularly those that control resources. The interests of these communities are often represented through professional associations. In workshops and forums over the past few years, certain aspects of professionalization have been acknowledged as useful goals that would advance the standing of RCD roles, and help organizations to find, hire, develop, and retain skilled professionals for these roles. Drawing from considerable organizational research on professions and professionalization, our discussions identified key steps toward RCD Professionalization:

Step 1: Establish an RCD professional association.

Step 2: Formalize and disseminate an RCD knowledge base.

Step 3: Implement education programs for RCD professionals and organizational managers.

The first two steps are major emphases of the RCD Resource and Career Center CI CoE pilot,⁶ which will provide a hub to gather and connect the many communities within the RCD domain. The topic of education programs has prompted a lively discussion in the community, and has been the focus of various workshops, etc. (e.g., at the ACM Practice and Experience in Research Computing (PEARC) conference series,^j which presents technical as well as organizational leading practices across traditional and emerging RCD applications and platforms). The needs for education are evolving with technology, with performance portability as a prime example of the challenge of keeping up with changing platforms.

Two additional steps to formalize education programs are sometimes described as part of the process of professionalization, however there is no consensus at this point that these additional steps are necessary or would be constructive:

Step 4: Establish academic RCD programs in universities.

Step 5: Create RCD graduate degree programs.

It is worth noting that there is also a tradition among traditional, well-established professions of controlled access and exclusion in order to monopolize a given domain (e.g., through legal licensure or regulation). Most of the RCD community feels this would be premature at best and some feel it would be antithetical to widely held principles of diversity, equity, and inclusivity. Furthermore, we currently see a need for rapid growth in the

^j <https://pearc.acm.org/>

number of RCD professionals, as most institutions are understaffed and struggle to meet the current demand from researchers.

LOOKING AHEAD

The RCD community has begun to understand itself as a distinct profession and is working to advance that profession. Many in the community are excited about this evolution, even as they recognize the long road to fully realize their ambitions. Looking ahead five years and imagining where RCD professionals must be to effectively partner with researchers to advance their research mission, several objectives stand out.

First: a broad professional association or society is needed that can be the common voice to advocate for the emerging RCD profession.

- › This association need not replace or subsume existing associations such as US-RSE, but rather should represent a voice for the broad RCD professional community, including people who support systems, software, data, network, security, and facilitation to the academic research community and their peers in the public and private sectors.
- › This association should have international membership, and must actively engage with national and regional groups as well as overlapping affinity groups such as the National Society of Black Engineers, the Society for Advancement of Chicanos/Hispanics and Native Americans in Science, and Women in High Performance Computing, to improve recruitment and retention of a more diverse RCD workforce.
- › The association must have a visible and active presence at current RCD events such as the Supercomputing and PEARC Conference series, the Research Data Access & Preservation Annual Summits, among many others.
- › The association should create a journal that provides a cross-disciplinary, international publication presenting peer-reviewed articles of high interest and educational value across the full range of RCD professional interests from case studies and leading practices to news to analyses of important trends, and more.

Second: the many disparate communities that are currently engaged in supporting RCD professionals must work together in a coordinated manner to address the big challenges, including in particular:

- › Communicating the essential role of RCD professionals in supporting research;

- › Demonstrating to students and young professionals that RCD roles are highly valued and provide exciting career paths;
- › Working with institutional leadership and funders to align research support priorities that ensure that RCD professionals are appropriately recognized and compensated so that we can recruit and retain these skilled staff to best support and sustain research;
- › Working with the community to curate and disseminate training models, practices, and materials to build and maintain the necessary RCD expertise.

Third: An expanded set of tools and services must be made available to the RCD professional community to accelerate the emergence of new RCD programs (e.g., at minority-serving institutions) and to advance the professional development of individuals, including:

- › Robust, standard models, and baseline data for program assessment and benchmarking;
- › Expanded support for consulting and mentoring to bring smaller and underfunded institutions into the community, to ensure broad access to RCD resources;
- › Sharing of proven models and leading practices for training and advancement, including internships as well as mid-career professional development;
- › Tools and advice for reducing structural barriers (e.g., in HR) to recruiting and retaining skilled RCD professionals.

This work builds upon an evolution that includes the work of the Campus Champions and the Advanced CyberInfrastructure—Research and Education Facilitators (ACI-REF^k) that gather the community and help to define RCD roles, as well as the activities of working groups at CaRCC, EDUCAUSE, and other organizations to explore and develop effective strategies, leading practices, and products to support RCD professionals and to advance the research mission. The new Research Computing and Data Resource and Career Center CoE is poised to take the next steps on this journey, and to catalyze the work of the RCD professional community to realize their full potential.

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^k <https://aciref.org/>

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